

Preparedness and Coaching Styles of the School Paper Advisers on Campus Journalism in the New Normal

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Abstract:

When the pandemic struck in 2020, the world was halted, including educational institutions and all their operations. The conduct of campus journalism activities deviated to a new schema, giving school paper advisers the challenges to overcome. This study aimed to determine the level of preparedness and coaching styles of the school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in a large sized schools division of Negros Oriental during the School Year 2021-2022 as a basis for a capability-building plan. The study focused on school paper advisers' level of preparedness and coaching styles considering their background knowledge, training, availability of resources, and facilitated learning. The study involved more young school paper advisers with shorter tenures as school paper advisers compared to old ones with longer experience as school paper advisers. Further, more teachers were handling higher levels compared to those handling lower levels. The results reveal that the respondents fared moderately in terms of preparedness. In this particular aspect, the area of training got the lowest mean. On the level of coaching styles, the respondents also fared moderately with the area of training having the lowest mean. Also, the study found no significant difference in the level of preparedness and coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The results of this study, calls for school paper advisers need training on preparedness and coaching styles on campus journalism in the new normal.

Keywords: preparedness, coaching styles, school paper advisers, school paper management, new normal, campus journalism

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

When the pandemic hit the Philippines and shut down educational institutions from face-to-face learning, numerous activities were put to a temporary halt as the country sought mitigation of cases. One of which is the conduct of the annual Press Conference where Campus Journalists (CJs) from the different regions convene to demonstrate their craft and expertise in the different categories of Campus Journalism. This annual activity converges campus writers to compete in both individual and group contests. The individual contest includes News Writing, Feature Writing, Editorial and Column Writing, Sports Writing, Copyreading and Headline Writing, Editorial Cartooning, Science-Technology Writing, and Photojournalism. The group contest includes Script and Radio Broadcasting, Script and TV Broadcasting, Collaborative Desktop Publishing, Online Publishing, and School Paper Contest.

The emerging challenge now is for the School Paper Advisers (SPAs) to acquire knowledge on the modification of campus journalism implementation at the new normal. Using this knowledge on journalistic modifications, it is expected that they can be prepared to adjust their coaching styles from the traditional to the now distance, electronic, and virtual. The need to conduct the study arose from this shift of learning both on the part of the teachers and the students. In a relevant study, teachers viewed online training and post-graduate studies to be potent factors in capacitating their relevant educational practices and aligning them with the learning modalities of education changed by the pandemic (Agaloos, 2020).

In this study, the researcher sought answers to the preparedness and coaching styles of SPAs in the new normal. The researcher saw the importance of this study considering there is an existing and active division organization of SPAs called the Negros Oriental School Paper Advisers' Association (NOSPAA) where campus journalism

developments may be cascaded, and issues and concerns may be addressed. If the SPAs were given the chance to air out their concerns, then they can respond to the challenges that the new normal poses as far as school paper management is concerned.

Current State of Knowledge

Chavez (2023) assessed the impact of the set of training entitled "Write Here, Right Now" whose aim is to develop skills in campus journalism particularly in the categories news writing, feature writing, sports writing, editorial writing, editorial cartooning, literary writing, photojournalism, and layout design. It explored the effectiveness and social impact of the set objectives toward the beneficiary elementary school. The assessment study further reported that "a community service project in an education sector helped in journalism skill building, establishing a school paper, and honing competitive individuals who excel in competitions during Press Conferences" (Chavez 2023). The beneficiaries evaluated the project to have served its purpose of fortifying the student journalists in terms of improving their journalistic skills and their acquired knowledge.

In a published study, Espadero (2022) evaluated the implementation of campus journalism in the Schools Division of Tandag City. Employing a descriptive survey method of research, the study described the extent of campus journalism implementation among the selected schools. Promoting responsible and free journalism, the schools committed to alleviating the journalistic skills of the students and strategically designated a school paper adviser to manage its operation. Several issues surfaced, which included "qualifications, relevant training, and security and tenure". Schools encountered other serious problems as revealed by the study. These included editorial policies, editorial board, school paper advisership, and financial aspects of campus journalism.

Estella (2015) assessed the current pedagogy of journalism in elementary schools in Los Banos and reported the existing problems in the preparedness of teachers in teaching journalism. The paper revealed that the teachers' unpreparedness accounted to the lack of formal training for both teachers and students, considering that journalism is not incorporated into the Basic Education Curriculum. The study also found that the problems encountered by school paper advisers are various: infrastructural, literacy-based, and appreciation-based. The lack of computers and strong internet connection account for infrastructural impediments while the incapacity of maximum use of the internet refers to the literacy issues. The apathy in using the internet as a means of learning is an appreciation-based issue.

Watt (2022) added that the rapid turn to online modes places second in the issues that the pandemic pedagogy addresses. As recommended, compassionate connection and interaction and quality and deep educational experience should support the targets of learning outcomes. More importantly in the journalism education, which is a facet of a school paper program, should be audience-focused and technology-empowered rather than technology-led.

Johnson (2016) also suggested that the thin line between coaches and administrators should be boldened by partnership. Identifying and developing an action plan is a concerted effort between a coach and an administrator, more so on implementation and monitoring. Stakeholders must also partake in the goals and actions toward success. Hiring professional and credible coaches likewise is a rigorous selection process to arrive at a clear and fair decision as Johnson proposed. A great deal of expectation is loaded on the shoulders of coaches or trainers in modeling lessons and aiding teachers in different instructional and management processes. Content is also a vital consideration in the process of evaluating possible coaches in any educational endeavor.

Brown (2016) presented a broad definition of professional development and coaching pertaining to education and teaching and provided a description of the features of a conceptual framework for coaching. To level up these two educational purposes, an examination of a coaching model using the conceptual framework supporting early language and literacy practices was provided. Prior knowledge is an important component of coaching according to Brown (2016). In consonance with the findings of Mansour and Kuzborska, Brown reported that teachers interpret new ideas and practices through the lens of what they know and do beforehand. The predispositions composed of pre-existing knowledge, skills, beliefs, and attitudes can have an impact on their interpretation, organization, and application of new information they received from professional development experiences.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The underpinning of significant theories aims at strengthening the claims of the study. One of the theories that has an impact on this study is the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which was developed by Icek Ajzen. Started as the Theory of Reasoned Action in 1980, the TPB "predicts an individual's intention to engage in a behavior at a specific time and place" (LaMorte 2022). The theory explains all behaviors that people have control over. Comprised of six constructs that collectively represent a person's actual control over behavior, the TPB states that behavioral achievement depends on both motivation (intention) and ability (behavioral control). It distinguishes between three types of beliefs - behavioral, normative, and control. The researcher sees the relevance of the constructs of the TPB and the significant areas of the study. According to LaMorte (2022), one of the constructs of

the TPB is attitude, which refers to “the degree to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation of the behavior of interest. It entails a consideration of the outcomes of performing the behavior”. The responses of the school paper advisers to questions on acquiring new knowledge, styles, and strategies in managing the school publication in the new normal would reflect their attitude to the task entrusted to them.

Motivational factors also influence a given behavior—where the stronger the intention to perform the behavior, the more likely the behavior will be performed. The behavioral intention construct of the TPB was identified to have a bearing on the study, specifically on the availability of training and resources that are necessary for the implementation of the campus journalism program.

Another construct of the TPB is the subjective norm, which refers to the belief about whether most people approve or disapprove of the behavior. “It relates to a person’s beliefs about whether peers and people of importance to the person think he or she should engage in the behavior” (LaMorte 2022). In light of facilitated learning, the subjective norm could have an impact to how the school paper advisers would perform their tasks. Social norms could also have an impact on the study. This refers to the customary codes of behavior in a group of people or a larger cultural context. While school paper advisers work independently in their respective schools, they also belong to a bigger social group of association of school paper advisers. It is then perceived that the school paper advisers’ sense of belonging could contribute to the possible needs to carry out the tasks entrusted to them. The other significant construct of the TPB is the Perceived power. This refers to the perceived presence of factors that may facilitate or impede performance of a behavior. Perceived power contributes to a person’s perceived behavioral control over each of those factors. In light of the study, these factors may come in structural or infrastructural needs, connectivity and technological amenities, and among others. Perceived power capacitates school paper advisers on how to handle these factors as they perform their tasks. Lastly, perceived behavioral control refers to “a person’s perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior of interest. Perceived behavioral control varies across situations and actions, which results in a person having varying perceptions of behavioral control depending on the situation” (LaMorte 2022). The study evaluates the advisers’ preparedness and coaching styles at a challenging phase of the pandemic. The contributions of philosophers like Jerome Bruner, Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky, and John Dewey to constructivism are said to be the inspiration for the birth of constructivism’s philosophical paradigm theory. Honebein (1996) asserted that this theory enables people to construct their own understanding and knowledge by experiencing things and reflecting on them. This aligns with the idea that people form or construct based on what they have experienced.

In line with the study, the constructivism philosophical paradigm theory helped determine the school paper advisers’ level of preparedness in responding to the challenges in school paper management in the new normal, and the same theory is hitched towards identifying the interest of the teachers in designing and conceptualizing coaching strategies given the pandemic situation that affected schools. Furthermore, this study was also anchored in David Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory where concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation are the stages that concretize learning. A key concept of this theory states that all these stages require learning styles as humans uniquely adopt varied styles for their own. In the light of the study, teachers need to know their learning styles as they will be handling students in a different mode of coaching. In the same way, this theory will also remind the teachers to look into the learning styles of their campus journalists to be effective in their coaching. This pandemic has facilitated the mode of coaching and SPAS must be exposed to experience, observation, conceptualization, and experimentation.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the levels of preparedness and coaching styles of the school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in a large-sized Schools Division in central Philippines during the School Year 2021-2022 as a basis for a capability-building plan. Specifically, this study sought to identify the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal according to the following areas: Background Knowledge, Training, Availability of Resources and Facilitated Learning. Likewise, the study sought the prevalent level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal according to the areas mentioned above. It also identified if there was a significant difference in the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when grouped and compared according to the research variables. Finally, it also examined if there was a significant difference in the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when they were grouped and compared according to the given variables.

Research Methodology:

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design, which is believed to be appropriate in measuring the level of preparedness and level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism and whether a significant difference exists when grouped and compared according to the variables, age, length of service as school paper advisers and grade level handled.

Respondents

The study's respondents were 87 school paper advisers of the elementary and secondary schools in a large sized schools division from a total population of 111. The researcher used stratified sampling, a random sampling technique, and the Cochran formula was applied to find the sample size since the number of respondents is quite large. To get the percentage, the respondents from each school were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The researcher randomly selects the respondents from each Congressional District using the lottery technique.

Instruments

A survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data to determine level of preparedness and level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism were it was subjected to validity (4.89=excellent) and reliability (0.957=excellent) for preparedness and (0.853=good) for coaching styles The questionnaire was divided into two parts wherein part I deals with the profile of respondents in terms of age, length of service as school paper advisers and grade level handled. Part 2 contained the questionnaire proper consisting of 56 items: 28 items were on the level of preparedness and 28 items on the level of coaching styles, 7-line items per area. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale, which contains the following scores: 5 – Always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – Rarely; and 1 – Almost Never.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the administration of the validity and reliability test of the research instrument, the researcher closely coordinated with the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent, the Public Schools District Supervisor, and the School Heads of all concerned schools for approval. Upon approval, the questionnaires were administered to target respondents. Due to the present safety protocols, the soft copy of the data-gathering instrument were sent through Google Forms. The link of the questionnaire were sent to the respondents through instant messaging. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allowed computer processing, statistical derivations, and tabular presentation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The analytical schemes employed to achieve the objectives of the study were determined by the nature of the research problem. Based on the concerns of this investigation, the following schemes were employed. Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal according to the these areas: background knowledge, training, availability of resources and facilitated learning. Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal according to the aforementioned areas. Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Objective No. 4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher ensures that respondents were given the free will to be involved in the study, their identity were not disclosed and they were assured of the confidentiality of the data gathered. After completion, all data stored in electronic gadgets were discarded in order to protect against unauthorized access or use of information. This research paper strived in earnest to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and protecting their anonymity throughout the entire research process. At the onset, this researcher secured their free, prior informed consent and assured them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Background Knowledge

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a School Paper Adviser in the New Normal, I...		
1. get updates on school paper management.	3.49	Moderate Level
2. receive new information on the various categories of in campus	3.62	High Level

journalism.

3. get the latest trends on writing necessary to learn.	3.40	Moderate Level
4. am supplemented with enough background information on a press conference's different individual writing categories.	3.33	Moderate Level
5. am supplemented with enough background information on the different group categories of a press conference.	3.34	Moderate Level
6. acquire knowledge on handling campus journalists concerning the categories they belong to.	3.53	High Level
7. voluntarily listen to informative talks and lectures on journalism to augment my background despite the challenges of the new normal.	3.94	High Level
Overall Mean	3.52	High Level

Table 1 shows the preparedness level of school paper advisers in campus journalism during the new normal with an overall mean of 3.52, indicating a high level of preparedness. The mean score is calculated by averaging the individual scores of various items that evaluate different aspects of advisers' preparedness in the context of the new normal. The item "I voluntarily listen to informative talks and lectures on journalism to augment my background despite the challenges of the new normal" received the highest mean score of 3.94, indicating a "High Level" of preparedness. This implies that school paper advisers actively pursue further knowledge and information on journalism by attending talks and lectures on their own. The user's dedication to ongoing learning is praiseworthy and in line with research that highlights the recommendation of arranging training programs that pertain to conducting online classes and designing course materials (Ramij, 2020). This is likewise in consonance with the study of De Villa and Ladia (2020) where teachers were advised to consider gathering resources, establishing practices, and profiling learners to suit online programs. In contrast, the item "I am supplemented with enough background information on a press conference's different individual writing categories" has the lowest mean score of 3.30, indicating a moderate level of preparedness. This suggests that advisers may lack up-to-date knowledge of current writing trends, which is in support of Glick's study in 2017, pointing out the problem among states when it comes to scholastic journalism and the training of journalism teachers.

The evolving nature of journalism and changing writing styles present challenges in guiding student journalists due to their moderate level of preparedness. Given this, schools divisions have the primal task to expose and engage the teachers to avenues that will address their stand on the matter. This strengthens the claim of Besa and Parcon (2018) of the effectiveness of having seasoned and experienced school paper advisers or resource persons for seminar workshops to augment the teachers' preparedness. This also conforms to the finding of Ladia (2015) that there is a need for campus journalists and their advisers to become fully aware of campus journalism, including its current trends to address the issues concerning its implementation. Advisers with the right and updated skills can effectively guide students in navigating the complexities of the modern media landscape, fostering a deeper understanding of journalism's societal role. The importance of advisers in developing journalistic skills among students is significant.

Table 2

Level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Training

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a School Paper Adviser in the New Normal, I...		
1. attend training-workshops to increase my knowledge of the latest in-campus journalism.	3.23	Moderate Level
2. attend training-workshops to enhance my journalistic writing skills.	3.30	Moderate Level
3. attend knowledge enhancement sessions on school paper management which are available for me to join.	3.28	Moderate Level
4. participate in available trainings on the different individual writing categories.	3.25	Moderate Level
5. participate in available trainings on the different group categories.	3.26	Moderate Level
6. avail of trainings from private institutions to enhance my knowledge and skills about campus journalism.	2.76	Moderate Level
7. collaborate with other school paper advisers to support my need for training despite the challenges of the new normal.	3.22	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.19	Moderate Level

Table 2 displays the average score of school paper advisers' preparedness in campus journalism, particularly in training, during the new normal. The overall mean for this aspect is 3.19. This falls within a moderately prepared range. The overall mean is calculated by averaging the individual means of items that measure advisers' involvement in on-campus journalism training activities. The average interpretation of preparedness in training is classified as "Moderate." This indicates that school paper advisers possess a moderate level of preparedness in training for campus journalism during the new normal. The item "attend training workshops to enhance my

journalistic writing skills" has the highest mean score of 3.30 in the table. This suggests that advisers generally possess moderate preparation in staying informed about various aspects of campus journalism. The high score suggests that advisers seek and obtain training relevant to different aspects of campus journalism, which is crucial for their role. This conforms to the study of Espadero (2022) which highlights that participation in journalism seminars, workshops, or conferences develops and polishes journalistic skills. Conversely, the lowest average score in the table is 2.76, which pertains to the item "seeking training from private institutions to improve my knowledge and skills in campus journalism." This item indicates that advisers may not often participate in external training programs provided by private institutions. A lower score suggests obstacles or difficulties in accessing or engaging in training opportunities like availability and cost. This result conforms with the study of Espadero (2022) where a problem on campus journalism enhancement surfaced in the actual implementation of journalistic programs.

Table 3
Level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Availability of Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Books, workbooks, and other reading and reference materials on school paper management in the new normal are available at the school level and are within my grasp.	2.92	Moderate Level
2. Books, workbooks, and other reading and reference materials on individual writing categories on campus journalism in the new normal are available at the school level and are within my grasp.	2.92	Moderate Level
3. Books, workbooks, and other reading and reference materials on group categories on campus journalism in the new normal are available at the school level and are within my grasp.	2.92	Moderate Level
4. The school has strong internet connectivity to support my program on campus journalism in the new normal.	3.49	Moderate Level
5. ICT equipment and amenities necessary for remote training on the different individual categories of campus journalism in the new normal are available in school.	3.54	High Level
6. ICT equipment and amenities necessary for remote training on the different group categories of campus journalism in the new normal are available in school.	3.43	Moderate Level
7. School funding is available for expenses on the implementation of campus journalism in the new normal.	3.64	High Level
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderate Level

Table 3 presents the average score of school paper advisers' preparedness in campus journalism under the new normal, specifically in the Availability of Resources category, which is 3.27. This falls within a moderately prepared range. The overall mean is calculated by averaging the individual means of items that measure the availability of resources for campus journalism activities. The highest mean is the seventh item that assesses the availability of school funding for expenses related to implementing campus journalism in the new normal. The data reveals a mean score of 3.64, suggesting an available moderate amount of funding. Adequate funding is crucial for journalism programs to thrive in the current environment. This positive development indicates the importance of having the necessary resources. It is emphasized in the study of Espadero (2022) that financial issues contribute to the hampering of journalism program implementations. Three items share the lowest mean spot. The mean scores for books, workbooks, and reference materials related to school paper management, and individual and group writing categories of campus journalism in the new normal are all 2.92, indicating a moderate level of availability. This suggests that although certain resources are available, there is potential for enhancing the accessibility of these materials for school paper advisers.

Table 4
Level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Facilitated Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. get updates on coaching campus journalists on the different individual writing categories.	3.68	High Level
2. get updates on coaching campus journalists on the different group categories.	3.74	High Level
3. am supplemented with enough background information on coaching in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.49	Moderate Level
4. acquire knowledge on coaching campus journalists concerning the categories they belong to in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.85	High Level
5. voluntarily listen to informative talks and lectures on journalism in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.86	High Level

6. collaborate with fellow school paper advisers in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal.	3.83	High Level
7. collaborate with bigger organizations and stakeholders in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal.	3.31	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.68	High Level

Table 4 shows that the overall mean of the level of preparedness of school paper advisers in campus journalism during the new normal, particularly in the area of Facilitated Learning, is 3.68. This falls within the range of high preparedness. The overall mean is calculated by averaging the individual means of different items that evaluate the preparedness of advisers in facilitating learning and coaching campus journalists during the new normal. The initial finding suggests that advisers exhibit a high level of readiness to receive updates on coaching campus journalists in specific writing categories, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.68. This implies that advisers have the requisite expertise and resources to effectively guide students in this area. The item "voluntarily listen to informative talks and lectures on journalism in a remote setup using any available platform" got the highest mean of 3.86, indicating that advisers have received sufficient support and necessary information for remote coaching activities voluntarily. This suggests that advisers show initiative and willingness to heighten their capacity using available platform means. This supports the study of De Villa and Manalo (2020) pointing out one of the five coping mechanisms to address the hurdles of the new normal: openness to new learning. Item 7, which pertains to collaboration with larger organizations and stakeholders in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal, indicates a need for improvement in external partnerships as it stands as the lowest mean. This indicates that the school paper advisers need to widen their scope to augment their skills. This conforms with the finding of Bedda et. al. (2023) highlighting the advantages of professional development through collaborative initiatives.

Table 5
Level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Background Knowledge

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a School Paper Adviser in the New Normal, I...		
1. get updates on coaching campus journalists on the different individual writing categories.	3.41	Moderate Level
2. get updates on coaching campus journalists on the different group categories.	3.34	Moderate Level
3. am supplemented with enough background information on coaching in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.46	Moderate Level
4. acquire knowledge on coaching campus journalists concerning the categories they belong to in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.57	High Level
5. voluntarily listen to informative talks and lectures on journalism in a remote setup using any available platform.	3.69	High Level
6. collaborate with fellow school paper advisers in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal.	3.75	High Level
7. collaborate with bigger organizations and stakeholders in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal.	3.17	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.49	Moderate Level

Table 5 examines the coaching styles of school paper advisers in the context of campus journalism during the new normal, with a specific emphasis on background knowledge. The initial finding suggests that advisers possess a moderate level of readiness in staying informed about coaching campus journalists in various writing categories, whose overall mean is 3.49. The item "collaborate with fellow school paper advisers in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal" obtained the highest mean of 3.75, interpreted as "High Level". In contrast, the item "collaborate with bigger organizations and stakeholders in acquiring background information on coaching in the new normal" got the lowest mean of 3.17, interpreted as "Moderate Level". The data implies that the school paper advisers make use of their linkages and connections with their fellows to get updated with the information they need. This proactive engagement of advisers in voluntary learning from their inner circles is an affirmation of the research of Dadayan (2021) saying that journalism training and workshops trigger excitement as new experiences provide opportunities to work with others. Meanwhile, the lowest mean about collaboration with bigger organizations and stakeholders compels the school paper advisers to mobilize their coordination with other institutions to continuously upgrade their levels and remain current in the changing field of campus journalism as underscored by Bedda et. al. (2023).

Table 6
Level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Training

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a School Paper Adviser in the New Normal, I...		

1. attend training-workshops to acquire knowledge on the latest on-campus journalism coaching.	3.22	Moderate Level
2. attend training-workshops to acquire knowledge on coaching styles in remote setup using any available platform.	3.21	Moderate Level
3. join available skill enhancement sessions on coaching styles.	3.21	Moderate Level
4. participate in trainings on new normal coaching in the different individual writing categories in a press conference.	3.22	Moderate Level
5. participate in trainings on coaching in the different group categories in a press conference.	3.22	Moderate Level
6. avail of trainings from private institutions to enhance my knowledge and skills in coaching in.	2.78	Moderate Level
7. collaborate with other school paper advisers to support my need for training on coaching.	3.38	Moderate Level
	3.18	Moderate Level

Table 6 displays the average coaching styles of school paper advisers in campus journalism during the new normal, with a specific focus on Training. The overall mean for this area is 3.18, which falls within the range of a moderate level of coaching styles. Moreover, the highest mean of 3.38, interpreted as "Moderate Level" was obtained by item number 7 "collaborate with other school paper advisers to support my need for training on coaching while the lowest mean of 2.78, interpreted as "Moderate Level" was obtained by item number 6 "avail of training from private institutions to enhance my knowledge and skills in coaching in". The highest mean indicates that advisers demonstrate a moderate level of proactivity in participating in training events to enhance their knowledge and coaching approaches. Item 7 evaluates the extent to which advisers engage in collaborative efforts with other school paper advisers to meet their training requirements in coaching. Ladia (2020) emphasized the establishment of journalistic practices, including collaborative learning, to escalate the levels of journalistic learning and teaching. Item 6 is noteworthy due to its lowest mean score of 2.78, suggesting a slightly diminished level of engagement. This item discusses how advisers can improve their coaching abilities by taking advantage of training opportunities offered by private institutions. The moderate level affirms the finding of Estella (2015) about the importance of formal training being a strong element of preparedness.

Table 7

Level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Availability of Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Division/District/School trainings on coaching in the new normal are available for me to participate in.	3.38	Moderate Level
2. Books, workbooks, and other reading and reference materials on individual writing categories coaching are available at the school level and are within my grasp.	3.18	Moderate Level
3. Books, workbooks, and other reading and reference materials on group categories coaching are available at the school level and are within my grasp.	3.24	Moderate Level
4. Outside my school, I have access to whatever resources and references I need to supplement my knowledge of coaching in the new normal.	3.51	High Level
5. I invite experienced school paper advisers to listen to and learn from their expertise on coaching in the new normal.	2.99	Moderate Level
6. I use the Internet to search for journalistic inputs I need for my background on coaching in the new normal.	3.91	High Level
7. School funding is available for expenses on coaching for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.64	High Level
Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Level

Table 7 presents the average score of school paper advisers' coaching styles in the context of campus journalism during the new normal. Specifically, the overall mean score for the Availability of Resources dimension is 3.41, which falls within the moderate range of coaching styles. The highest mean is obtained by item number 6, which is "I use the Internet to search for journalistic inputs I need for my background on coaching in the new normal". With a mean of 3.91, this item falls under the "High Level" interpretation. Meanwhile, item number 7, "I invite experienced school paper advisers to listen to and learn from their expertise on coaching in the new normal" got the lowest mean of 2.99, interpreted as "Moderate Level". The result reveals that advisers demonstrated a significant reliance on the Internet (with a mean score of 3.91) to access journalistic resources relevant to their coaching expertise. This finding supports the report of Yan (2021) that teachers can be best groomed for the online setup of teaching using one of the four prongs, which is technology access. The mean score for the item assessing the tendency of advisers to invite experienced school paper advisers for peer learning was 2.99, indicating room for

improvement in this area. To reiterate, tapping the expertise of seasoned school paper advisers and manpower can be a strong force in the enhancement of journalistic skills (Besa et.al. 2018).

Table 8

Level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal area of Facilitated Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Campus journalism experts in the division provide inputs that add to my knowledge on coaching for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.74	High Level
2. I seek assistance from seasoned school paper advisers in the light of coaching for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.76	High Level
3. School administrators involve themselves in the planning, organizing, and monitoring of coaching programs for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.60	High Level
4. Guest and resource speakers I listened to about campus journalism provided substantial and comprehensive background information on coaching for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.77	High Level
5. Guest and resource speakers, I listened to about coaching for campus journalism in the new normal provided substantial and comprehensive background information on the different individual writing categories.	3.80	High Level
6. Guest and resource speakers, I listened to about coaching for campus journalism in the new normal provided substantial and comprehensive background information on the different group categories.	3.79	High Level
7. Other stakeholders provide technical assistance on coaching for campus journalism in the new normal.	3.38	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.69	High Level

Table 8 revealed that the overall mean for the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Facilitated Learning is 3.69, which is interpreted as "High Level". In this category, item number 5 referring to "Guest and resource speakers, I listened to about coaching for campus journalism in the new normal provided substantial and comprehensive background information on the different individual writing categories" stood out with the highest mean of 3.80, interpreted as "High Level". In contrast, item number 7 on "Other stakeholders provide technical assistance on coaching for campus journalism in the new normal" obtained the lowest mean of 3.38, interpreted as "Moderate Level". The table investigates the accessibility of training experts for advisers to enhance their understanding of recent advancements in campus journalism. In light of facilitation from mentors and trainers, the advisers received a high level of information that is tantamount to their coaching and managing the school paper. This aligns with the study of Njuguna (2020) pointing out that the emergence of training factors, including resource persons, are indicators of effective training. On the other side, the technical assistance on coaching for campus journalism by other stakeholders stands with the lowest mean of 3.38, which indicates that there is a low involvement from outside entities and support systems that could improve the advisers' status. This concurs with the finding of Kombaso et. al. (2015) highlighting the value of mingling and coordinating with their fellows and administrators in effective coaching.

Table 9

Difference in the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Background Knowledge when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	43.78	914.000	0.925		Not Significant
	Older	37	44.30				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	40.72	750.500	0.148	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	48.65				
Grade Handled	Level Lower	33	44.68	868.500	0.844		Not Significant
	Higher	54	43.58				

Table 9 presents an analysis of variations in preparedness levels among school paper advisers based on their age, length of service as school paper advisers, and the grade level they handle. The Mann-Whitney U test results suggest that there is no statistically significant variation in preparedness when considering these variables.

Regardless of age, length of service, or grade level, advisers in campus journalism demonstrate similar levels of preparedness in terms of background knowledge in the new normal. Glick (2017) highlighted the importance of inclusive professional development for educators at all stages of their careers. This is consistent with the lack of significant differences in preparedness observed among different age groups and lengths of service. Bright (2020) emphasizes the importance of training programs that address the diverse needs of educators across different grade levels. The lack of notable variations in preparedness across different grade levels supports this viewpoint.

Table 10

Difference in the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Training when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	44.93	878.500	0.689		Not Significant
	Older	37	42.74				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	40.15	721.500	0.089	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	49.46				
Grade Handled	Lower	33	46.06	823.000	0.551		Not Significant
	Higher	54	42.74				

Table 10 examines the variations in preparedness regarding training among school paper advisers, categorized by Age, Length of Service as School Paper Advisers, and Grade Level Handled. The Mann-Whitney U test results, like Table 35, suggest no significant differences in preparedness across these variables. Advisers of varying ages, lengths of service, and grade levels exhibit similar levels of preparedness in terms of training for campus journalism in the new normal. Njuguna (2020) found that the effectiveness of training programs depends on their provision of current and pertinent knowledge and skills, irrespective of educators' demographic characteristics. The results in both tables confirm this idea, as there are no significant variations in preparedness among advisers with different backgrounds. According to Brown (2019), younger educators may need training to develop basic teaching skills, while older, more experienced educators may seek professional development opportunities to stay current with evolving pedagogical approaches and technology. The lack of significant differences in both tables indicates that training programs are tailored to meet the diverse needs of educators, regardless of their age. This ensures that they are well-prepared for the challenges of campus journalism in the new normal. According to Smith et al. (2020), both experienced and newer educators can benefit from training. Experienced educators can benefit from training that helps them stay updated with the latest pedagogical trends and technology. On the other hand, newer educators may require foundational training. The lack of significant differences in both tables suggests that training programs are designed to meet the changing needs of advisers at different career stages, preparing them for the new challenges in campus journalism. Smith et al. (2020) highlight the importance of tailoring training programs to address the distinct needs of educators working with different grade levels. The lack of significant differences in both tables indicates that training programs effectively equip advisers with the necessary knowledge and skills for campus journalism, regardless of the grade levels they work with. This ensures their preparedness for the challenges posed by the new normal.

Table 11

Difference in the level of preparedness of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Availability of Resources when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	45.74	838.000	0.454		Not Significant
	Older	37	41.65				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	43.83	909.500	0.941	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	44.24				
Grade Handled	Lower	33	43.68	880.500	0.927		Not Significant
	Higher	54	44.19				

Table 11 assesses the preparedness of school paper advisors in terms of resource availability. Advisors are categorized according to their age, length of service as school paper advisors, and the grade level they handle. The Mann-Whitney U test results suggest that there are no statistically significant differences in preparedness between the groups. This implies that school paper advisors, regardless of their age, years of service, or the grade levels they work with, consistently exhibit preparedness in ensuring the availability of resources for campus journalism in the current educational landscape. Table 37's findings support the existing educational literature, emphasizing the significance of providing educators with equitable access to resources (Andarwulan et al., 2021). Equitable resource access is a crucial principle in education, ensuring that educators possess the essential tools and materials for delivering quality education. In this context, it suggests that school paper advisors have equal access to the necessary resources for effective coaching in campus journalism, regardless of their age or years of service. The lack of significant differences in preparedness among educators based on demographic characteristics aligns with the principles of inclusive professional development (Agalos et al., 2020). Inclusive professional development seeks to address the diverse needs of educators, acknowledging that their effectiveness and preparedness are influenced by multiple factors. Inclusivity guarantees that training and resources are accessible and flexible for educators of various age groups, lengths of service, and grade levels.

Table 12
Difference in the level of preparedness of school paper advisors on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Facilitated Learning when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	46.16	817.000	0.353		Not Significant
	Older	37	41.08				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	41.86	809.000	0.346	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	47.03				
Grade Handled	Lower	33	44.06	889.000	0.986		Not Significant
	Higher	54	43.96				

Table 12 examines the variations in preparedness regarding facilitated learning among school paper advisors, taking into account factors such as Age, Length of Service as School Paper Advisers, and Grade Level Handled. The Mann-Whitney U test results, like Table 37, indicate no significant differences in preparedness among the variables. This suggests that advisors of different age groups, lengths of service, and responsibilities for different grade levels demonstrate similar levels of preparedness in facilitating learning for campus journalism in the new normal. The results presented align with the existing educational research that highlights the importance of providing equal training opportunities for educators (Brown, 2019). Equitable training ensures educators' access to professional development for skill and knowledge enhancement. The lack of significant differences in demographic characteristics implies that school paper advisors have equal opportunities for facilitated learning, regardless of their age, years of service, or the grade levels they teach. Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of facilitated learning environments, which involve expert input and peer collaboration, in promoting knowledge acquisition and skill development among educators (Wilson et al., 2022). The lack of significant differences in preparedness suggests that facilitated learning opportunities effectively cater to the varied requirements of school paper advisors, ensuring their readiness for the new normal in campus journalism.

Table 13
Difference in the level of coaching styles of school paper advisors on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Background Knowledge when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	46.92	779.000	0.208		Not Significant
	Older	37	40.05				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	41.27	779.000	0.229	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	47.86				
Grade Handled	Lower	33	42.94	856.000	0.759		Not Significant
	Higher	54	44.65				

Table 13 investigates the variations in coaching styles among school paper advisers based on their Background Knowledge in campus journalism. Advisers are classified based on age, length of service, and the grade level they handle. The Mann-Whitney U test results suggest that there is no statistically significant variation in coaching styles when considering these variables. Regardless of factors such as age, years of service, or grade levels taught, school paper advisers demonstrate similar coaching styles in relation to their knowledge of campus journalism. Inclusive professional development seeks to address the diverse needs of educators, acknowledging that their coaching styles may differ while still being equally effective (Johnson et al. 2021). In this context, coaching practices are inclusive and adaptable to educators of diverse demographics and professional backgrounds. Coaching practices play a crucial role in facilitating effective knowledge and skill transfer from educators to students (Smith & Wilson, 2019). Although there is limited literature on coaching practices of school paper advisers, the lack of significant differences in coaching styles based on demographic characteristics indicates that advisers employ equally effective practices in teaching background knowledge in campus journalism.

Table 14

Difference in the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Training when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	45.63	843.500	0.482		Not Significant
	Older	37	41.80				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	42.64	848.500	0.547	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	45.93				
Grade Handled	Level	Lower	33	869.500	0.850		Not Significant
		Higher	54				

Table 14 examines the variations in coaching methods employed by school paper advisers within the framework of campus journalism training. Advisers, like those in Table 39, are classified based on Age, Length of Service, and Grade Level Handled. The Mann-Whitney U test results indicate no significant differences in coaching styles based on the examined variables. This implies that advisers of different age groups, years of service, and grade levels utilize comparable coaching approaches in training for campus journalism in the current context. Coaching practices in education aim to address the varied needs of educators. In contemporary education, inclusivity is crucial due to the challenges educators encounter and the need to adapt to new teaching modalities, such as remote and online learning. The absence of significant differences in coaching styles based on demographic characteristics implies that coaching practices are flexible and successful in meeting the specific requirements of individual educators, including those who serve as school paper advisers. The goal of effective coaching in education is to improve educators' skills and competencies. Knight (2019) suggests that the process includes offering specific feedback, establishing objectives, and promoting reflective practices. Although the skills needed for school paper advisers may vary from those of classroom teachers, the principles of skill development through coaching remain applicable.

Table 15

Difference in the level of coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal in the area of Availability of Resources when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	50	44.76	887.000	0.743		Not Significant
	Older	37	42.97				
Length of Service as School Paper Adviser	Sorter	51	43.50	892.500	0.825	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	36	44.71				
Grade Handled	Level	Lower	33	787.000	0.361		Not Significant
		Higher	54				

Table 15 examines the Availability of Resources and compares coaching styles based on three variables: Age, Length of Service as School Paper Adviser, and Grade Level Handled. The analysis found no significant

difference in coaching styles between younger and older advisers in terms of resource availability. The p-value, which was greater than the predetermined significance level of 0.05, suggests that age does not have a significant impact on coaching styles in this particular context. The second variable, Length of Service as School Paper Adviser, did not show a significant result. The study found no significant relationship between the length of service of advisers and the impact of resource availability on coaching styles. Coaching styles in campus journalism pertain to the methods and approaches utilized by school paper advisers to mentor and guide student journalists. Lopez (2017) describes a range of practices within these styles, which involve advisers facilitating learning, providing support, and efficiently managing resources in the context of campus journalism. School paper advisers play a crucial role in shaping the experiences of student journalists. Their responsibilities include advising on journalism practices such as writing, editing, and ethical standards. Advisers have the responsibility of supervising the production process of school publications. Garcia (2019) asserts that they have a significant impact on fostering a favorable atmosphere for journalism education and training. Age can influence advisers' familiarity and comfort with digital resources and technology. Younger advisers, due to their familiarity with technology, may have coaching styles that are influenced by their immersion in a technologically rich environment. Moreover, the tenure as a school paper adviser can have an impact. Experienced advisers may have developed effective resource management strategies and enhanced their ability to facilitate learning. Adaptability to changing resource availability is crucial. The grade level overseen by advisers can also influence outcomes. Advisers at higher grade levels may face distinct expectations and resource needs compared to those working with lower grade levels.

Conclusions

The study involved more young school paper advisers with shorter tenures as school paper advisers compared to old ones with longer experience as school paper advisers. Further, more teachers were handling higher levels compared to those handling lower levels. On the level of preparedness, the school paper advisers are at the moderate level. The advisers expressed the need for more training on campus journalism preparedness. In terms of coaching styles, the school paper advisers prevalently fared moderately in most areas. There is also a need for school paper advisers to seek more training and opportunities to improve their coaching skills. When grouped according to the different study variables, the advisers consistently showed moderation in the aspect of preparedness, specifically in the areas of training and availability of resources. This consistency is likewise evident in view of the advisers' coaching styles. It is then concluded that there is a need for more training, exposure, enhancement, and provisions to augment the preparedness and coaching strategies of school paper advisers. The study found no significant difference in the levels of preparedness and coaching styles of school paper advisers on campus journalism in the new normal when grouped and compared according to the study variables. The study results calls for the school paper advisers to be given more training to augment their knowledge and fortify their training capabilities. Likewise, sources that are instrumental to the success of the implementation of campus journalism programs should be made more available alongside facilitated learning from experts. Collaborate with school administrators to provide support and resources to school paper advisers. Integrate journalism-related modules and training into the curriculum to offer standardized guidance and support to school paper advisers. Involve campus journalists in further studies to bring the study to a wider perspective.

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